

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES ON FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. This thesis examines innovative approaches in foreign language teaching, focusing on how present strategies and technologies enhance language learning. It explores methods such as gamification, CLIL, and the use of digital tools, apps, and social media. By exploring current research and practical applications, the study highlights the effectiveness of these approaches and offers insights for educators aiming to improve language instruction in diverse contexts.

Keywords: Foreign language teaching, innovative methods, task-based learning, gamification, CLIL, educational technology, language teaching apps

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezis chet tilini o'qitishda innovatsion yondashuvlarni o'rganadi va zamonaviy strategiyalar hamda texnologiyalar til o'rganishni qanday samarali tarzda yaxshilashini tahlil qiladi. Unda gamifikatsiya (til o'rganishni qiziqarli qilish uchun turli xil o'yin elementlaridan foydalanish), CLIL (fan va tilni integratsiyalashgan holda o'qitish), raqamli vositalar, ilovalar va ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan foydalanish kabi usullar ko'rib chiqiladi. Amaliy qo'llanmalar va zamonaviy tadqiqotlarga tayangan holda, ushbu tadqiqot bu yondashuvlarning samaradorligini ko'rsatadi hamda turli metodlarda til o'qitishni rivojlantirmoqchi bo'lgan o'qituvchilar uchun muhim tavsiyalarni taklif etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: chet tilini o'qitish, innovatsion usullar, gamifikatsiya, CLIL, ta'lim texnologiyalari, til o'rgatuvchi ilovalar

Introduction

Learning a foreign language provides deeper insights into diverse cultures, fostering empathy and understanding. It allows people to appreciate different traditions, values, and worldviews. Multilingual individuals often improve better communication skills, as they can express themselves in multiple languages and understand nuances in different linguistic contexts. In today's globalized world, proficiency in foreign languages is increasingly commended as a vital skill. Traditional methods of language instruction have been supplemented and, in some cases, replaced by innovative approaches that capitalize on technology, cognitive science, and pedagogical research. By accepting innovative techniques such as immersive virtual environments, gamification, adaptive learning platforms, and communicative language teaching educators can better meet the diverse needs of learners and enrich more effective language acquisition. In recent years, advancements in technology and insights from cognitive science have revolutionized the field of language education. Innovative methods of teaching foreign languages have emerged, providing new ways to engage learners, personalise instruction, and facilitate language acquisition. This article

explores several innovative ways that have gained traction in language classrooms worldwide. Immersive virtual environments (IVEs) represent a cutting-edge approach in language education, taking advantage of the power of virtual reality (VR) technology to create dynamic and engaging learning experiences.

In developing countries like Ethiopia, Malaysia, and Mozambique, the market for English language learning is red hot. These are places where, often, English proficiency is seen as a stepping stone to a better job and a one-way ticket out of poverty. But one major kink in that plan is the fact that in many cases, the English teachers within these countries don't speak English either. And so, the cycle continues.

But Luis von Ahn believes his app could play a key role in breaking that cycle. Von Ahn is the co-founder of Duolingo, a free language learning app that launched two and a half years ago and has since amassed a whopping 60 million users worldwide. It not only provided the opportunity to learn English for free but also made it easy and interesting to learn. It gave children of school age and even older the chance to learn languages through innovative methods using electronic devices

Gamification has emerged as a powerful strategy to increase motivation and engagement in language learning, leveraging elements of gameplay to transform the learning experience into a dynamic and enjoyable attempt. By incorporating game-like features such as points, badges, and leaderboards into language learning apps and platforms, gamification captivates learners' attention and encourages active participation. One of the key benefits of gamification is its ability to tap into intrinsic motivation — the internal desire to engage in an activity for its own sake. By introducing elements of challenge, achievement, and progression, gamified language learning activities stimulate learners' curiosity. As learners win points, open achievements, and climb leaderboards, they experience a sense of accomplishment and fulfilment, fuelling their desire to continue learning.

How Content and Language Intergraded Learning method (CLIL) impact university students' English learning outcomes in non-English as native-speaking countries? The study attempts to use a systematic literature review method to look through various peer-reviewed journal articles about the implementation of CLIL and its influence on learners' English acquisition in higher education from three perspectives: general English proficiency, productive and receptive language skills outcomes, and students' attitudes. Findings demonstrate that English ability has improved after CLIL — based lessons, while the difference between the CLIL group and non-CLIL group is not significant, and different linguistic abilities are unevenly developed. Meanwhile, students gain motivation and interest to learn English in CLIL, while some say they feel challenged in learning English by the new teaching method. Based on these findings, the study

provides recommendations and teaching strategies implications for introducing CLIL in universities.

Virtual exchange is known as a field of computer-assisted language learning (CALL) as it relates to the use of technology in language learning. Outside the field of language education, this type of pedagogic practice is being used to internationalise the curriculum and offer students the opportunity to engage with peers in other parts of the world in collaborative online projects.

There has been the application of multiple names to what is meant by practice, ranging from names that usually refer to one specific practice in the area, such as dual language virtual exchange, that at times also goes by the name of tele-tandem, which means language acquisition that involves reciprocal language exchange between tandem partners. In this method, each learner ideally serves as a native speaker of the language the other person intends to learn. More generic terms for virtual exchange are tandem language learning, globally virtual connections, online interaction and exchange, online intercultural exchange, online exchange, virtual exchange, virtual connections, global virtual teams, globally-networked learning environments, collaborative online international learning (COIL), Internet-mediated intercultural foreign language education, globally networked learning, and telecollaboration. Virtual exchange is the most commonly known umbrella term at present, one that can be used to refer to numerous models and practices.

Conclusion

Approaches to foreign language teaching, highlighting how strategies like task-based learning, gamification, CLIL, and virtual exchanges — alongside digital tools such as AI and language apps — improve language acquisition. These methods not only improve learner engagement and motivation but also support the development of communication skills and cultural understanding.

Research shows that while challenges exist, such as uneven skill development in CLIL or limited teacher proficiency in some regions, the overall impact of these innovations is positive. Tools like Duolingo have made language learning more accessible, fostering language learning skills.

As education evolves, blending traditional methods with technological innovation provides educators with effective ways to meet learners' diverse needs. These evolving practices mark a significant shift toward more engaging, inclusive, and effective language methods in a global context.

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